

FLOW VISUALIZATION AND MODELING OF THE RESIN INFUSION PROCESS DURING MANUFACTURE OF FIBER METAL LAMINATES BY VARTM

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SUMMARY

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs) have been successfully manufactured by the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process developed at NASA Langley Research Center. A flow visualization fixture of the FML, VARTM process was constructed and used to observe the resin infiltration process. Results of the flow visualization experiments are reported and compared with the predictions of a VARTM process simulation model.

Keywords: vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), fiber metal laminate (FML), process simulation model, flow visualization

INTRODUCTION

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs) are fabricated by stacking alternate layers of metallic sheets and fiber-reinforced polymeric-matrix prepreg plies [1]. Two common FMLs include ARALL™ and GLARE™. ARALL™ uses unidirectional aramid fiber while GLARE™ uses either unidirectional or biaxial high strength glass fiber. Both laminates use aluminum alloys for the metallic sheets. FMLs have mechanical and environmental properties that are superior compared with monolithic metal alloys or fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite laminates.

FMLs are currently manufactured by placing the layup of metallic sheets and prepreg plies in a mold and exposing the structure to elevated temperature and pressure in a compression press or an autoclave. These manufacturing methods result in well consolidated structures with good bonding between the metallic sheets and the fiber-reinforced composite. However, these fabrication processes are expensive and the part size is limited by the size of the press or autoclave. In order to overcome these limitations, a program is underway to investigate the manufacture of FMLs by the low-cost VARTM process.

The VARTM process used in this investigation is based on the process documented in Reference [2]. In the VARTM process, resin flow is primarily in the transverse direction which requires that resin pathways be inserted into the metal foils. A schematic diagram of one possible resin infiltration scheme is shown in Figure 1. The size and shape of the pathways must be large enough to permit resin to flow into and

wet-out the glass fabrics, but small enough as to not compromise the structural performance of the FML.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of one possible infiltration scheme.

In this investigation, a combined experimental and numerical study was performed to investigate resin flow into the glass fabrics of the hybrid perform during the resin infusion stage of the VARTM process. A flow visualization fixture was constructed which permitted the resin flow patterns to be observed at both the top and bottom surfaces of the preform during infiltration. The flow visualization data were compared with the results of a simulation model used to predict resin flow into the hybrid perform.

FLOW VISUALIZATION TESTS

The resin will be infused into the dry reinforcing fiber by a VARTM type process and will also bond the metal sheets to the reinforcing fiber layers. Since resin flow in a VARTM process is primarily in the through-the-thickness or transverse direction, resin pathways must be inserted into the metal foils to allow infiltration between layers. Obviously, the size, shape and arrangement of the pathways will impact the infiltration of resin into the preform.

Fixture Components

The visualization fixture, shown in Figure 2, is identical to the VARTM fixture currently used to manufacture FMLs except for the changes noted below which were necessary to observe the fluid during infiltration. A clear, scratch resistant, polycarbonate tool plate was used in place of the metal tool plate. The dimensions of the tool were 0.914 m long by 0.508 m wide. Three 0.95 cm diameter holes were drilled and tapped into the plate for the resin inlet and vacuum connections. The resin inlet tube is shown on the right and the vacuum outlet tube is shown on the left.

Acetate, clear plastic film, 0.381 mm thick, was used in place of the aluminum sheet. Resin pathways were machined into the acetate films to permit resin flow through the films during processing. The remaining components and all dimensions of the visualization fixture are identical to the VARTM fixture. Mounted below the polycarbonate tool was a mirror which was used to observe the resin flow along the bottom surface of the preform. Use of the mirror allows the video camera to

simultaneously record the flow fronts on both the top and bottom surfaces of the preform.

Figure 2. Flow visualization fixture.

Hybrid Preform

The preform consists of 5 sheets of the 0.381 mm thick acetate and 4 layers of S-glass fabric. The dimensions of the acetate sheets and S-glass fabric were 0.356 m by 0.356 m. The reinforcement was 8.9 oz, S-2-glass fiber, 8-Harness Satin Weave, Style 6781 biaxial fabric. The distribution medium placed on top of the preform consisted of 3 layers of polyethylene fabric. A schematic diagram of the hybrid preform lay up is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of hybrid preform lay up.

Circular resin pathways were machined into the acetate films using a precision drill fixture. A 3-axis digital readout was used to accurately determine where on acetate

films the pathways were to be drilled. The spacing of the circular pathways used in the present investigation is shown in Figure 4. Three different pathway hole diameters were used: 0.41 mm, 0.83 mm and 1.59 mm.

Figure 4. Spacing of the pathways in the acetate films.

Test Procedure

The layup shown in Figure 3 was vacuum bagged and held under a vacuum of 724 mm Hg for at least 30 minutes prior to infiltration. The infiltrating fluid was SAE 40 W motor oil with a viscosity of 0.24 Pa·s. The oil was degassed in a vacuum chamber for 30 minutes before the test. The fluid flow patterns on the top and bottom surfaces of the preform were recorded during infiltration using a digital movie camera.

VARTM SIMULATION MODEL

A simulation model of the FML, VARTM process was developed using the computational fluid dynamics code FLUENT. A volume of fluid (VOF) multiphase model was adopted to model the filling process. The numerical scheme ensured first order accuracy in time interpolation and second order accuracy in space interpolation.

A schematic diagram of the hybrid preform showing the boundary conditions used in the simulations is shown in Figure 5. The resin injection port was modeled as a square pressure inlet, which has the same cross sectional area as the circular injection port used in the tests. This was done to preserve the uniformity of the model mesh and to avoid long computation time. The boundaries of the distribution media were defined as a “wall” boundary condition, except for the left-end face which was defined as a “pressure outlet” boundary condition. In order to include the effect of race-tracking on two sides of the mold, two air gaps, each 4 mm wide, were added to two sides of the preform. “Pressure outlet” boundary conditions were specified at the left-end (resin outlet side) of the air gaps and the four layers of glass fabric. The side faces of the glass fabric, in contact with the air gaps, were defined as an “interior boundary” to allow resin to leak into the air gap.

The acetate films were modeled using the “porous jump” boundary condition. Porous jump conditions are used to model thin membranes with known velocity (pressure-drop) characteristics and are a 1D simplification of the porous media model available for cell zones. Compared to the full porous media model, the porous jump model yields satisfactory results while saving computation time and has better convergence.

Figure 5. Boundary conditions used in the simulations.

A three dimensional mesh of the hybrid preform was constructed using the mesh generator GAMBIT. The mesh included 12882 hexahedral cells and is shown in Figure 6.

The distribution medium and glass fabrics were assumed to be porous materials. The permeabilities of the glass fabric at 1 atm compaction pressure and a porosity of 0.558 were taken from reference [3]. For the distribution medium, the permeabilities for a porosity of 0.75 were taken from reference [4]. Numerical values for the permeabilities used in the simulations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Permeabilities of the distribution medium and glass fabrics

	S_x (m ²)	S_y (m ²)	S_z (m ²)
Distribution medium	8.31×10^{-9}	8.31×10^{-9}	5.49×10^{-10}
Glass fabric	1.0225×10^{-10}	1.6015×10^{-10}	3.0305×10^{-11}

The transverse permeability of the acetate films was estimated from the model described by Roy, Tan and Pillai for circular holes in a plate [5]

$$S_{theory} = \frac{n\pi R^4}{8A} \quad (1)$$

where, n is the number of the holes, R is the radius of the hole and A is the area of the acetate film. The permeabilities of the acetate films with 189 holes and hole diameters of 0.41 mm, 0.83 mm and 1.59 mm are $1.0 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$, $1.60 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$, and $2.33 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$, respectively.

Figure 6. Three dimensional mesh of the hybrid preform and distribution media.

RESULTS

The results of the infiltration experiments are shown in Figures 7 – 10. The three hybrid preforms with different flow pathway hole diameters were successfully infiltrated using the VARTM process. The glass fabrics in each of the hybrid preforms appeared to be completely wet-out with fluid and no significant dry spots were detected. The flow patterns on the top surface of the hybrid preform with the smallest flow pathway hole diameter (0.41 mm) are shown in Figure 7. As expected, the flow pathway hole diameter did not have a significant affect on the flow into the distribution media or the top surface of the hybrid preform. Total wet-out of the distribution media was achieved in about 30 seconds for all cases. Beneath the photographs of the flow patterns are the results of the FLUENT VARTM simulation at the corresponding times. The scale bar

Figure 7. Flow patterns on the top surface of the hybrid preform with the 0.41 mm flow pathway hole diameter.

beneath the simulation results represents the volume fraction of fluid in the hybrid preform. The color red represents a volume fraction of fluid of 1, or fully saturated. The color blue represents a volume fraction of fluid of 0, or completely dry. Overall, the model was able to capture the basic shape of the flow patterns. However, the absolute times do not match very well which is understandable since literature values were used for the permeabilities of the glass fabric and distribution media.

Figure 8. Flow patterns on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform with the 0.41 mm flow pathway hole diameter.

Figure 9. Flow patterns on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform with the 0.83 mm flow pathway hole diameter.

The flow patterns, at the bottom surface of the glass fabric next to the tool plate, are shown in Figures 8 – 10. As expected, the flow path hole diameter had a significant effect on the both the basic shape of the pattern and the amount of time required to completely wet-out the hybrid preform. As the flow path hole diameter increases, filling of the hybrid preform becomes dominated by transverse flow through the acetate films and glass fabric. This results in a significant reduction in total fill time. For example, increasing the diameter of the holes in the acetate films from 0.41 mm to 0.83 mm, results in a decrease in the total fill time from about 30 minutes to 8.5 minutes.

Beneath the photographs of the flow patterns are the VARTM simulation results at similar times. The VARTM simulation, with the porous jump boundary condition for the acetate films, captures the basic shape of the flow patterns quite well for the case of the smallest flow pathway hole diameter. However, as the flow pathway hole diameter increases, and transverse flow dominates the filling process, the calculated flow patterns look very different. Obviously this is due to modeling the flow through discrete holes in acetate films as a porous material. Further, the model used to estimate the transverse permeability in the acetate film is probably not very accurate since the hole diameter is close to or greater than the film thickness. The VARTM simulation was able to capture partial saturation of the bottom layer, observed as the flow patterns with colors between blue and red. However, there is no direct way to relate the partial saturation of simulation predicted flow patterns to the observed flow patterns.

Figure 10. Flow patterns on the bottom surface of the hybrid preform with the 1.59 mm flow pathway hole diameter.

The VARTM simulation can be used to observe the flow patterns in each of the glass fabric layers to determine how resin infuses the hybrid perform during infiltration. Shown in Figure 11 are the flow patterns on the top surface of each of the 4 layers of glass fabric, with layer 1 being closest to the distribution media and layer 4 being closest to the tool plate. As expected, the layers closest to the distribution media are infused first.

At 2 minutes

At 5 minutes

Figure 11. Flow patterns on the top surface of the glass fabric layers during infiltration of the hybrid preform with the 0.41 mm flow pathway hole diameter.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A flow visualization fixture of the FML, VARTM process was constructed and used to observe the resin infiltration process. Results of the flow visualization experiments showed that FMLs can be successfully manufactured by the VARTM process when flow pathways are machined into the metal foils. The size of the flow pathways significantly influences the shape of the flow patterns and the total infiltration time. A simulation model of the FML, VARTM process was developed using the commercial software package FLUENT. The acetate films, with the flow paths machined into them, were modeled using the “porous jump” boundary condition. Overall, the model was able to capture the basic shapes of the flow patterns. However, the absolute times do not match well due to the use of literature values for the permeabilities of the glass fabric and distribution media. Experiments are underway to measure the permeabilities of the glass fabrics, distribution media and acetate films with machined flow pathways of different diameters. A new FLUENT model will be developed which gives a better description of the flow pathways in the acetate films.

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